

MEDICAL SCIENCES

SYSTEMIC INVOLVEMENT IN BRUCELLOSIS

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Abstract

Brucellosis is a widely prevalent zoonotic infection with polymorphic clinical manifestations and frequent multisystem involvement. The intracellular survival of bacteria of the genus *Brucella*, predominantly within macrophages, allows evasion of the host immune response, promotes chronic inflammation, and leads to progressive damage across multiple organs and systems, including the musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, nervous, gastrointestinal, genitourinary, hematologic, respiratory, dermatologic, and visual systems.

This review summarizes current evidence on the systemic manifestations and complications of brucellosis, with a focus on osteoarticular involvement, neurobrucellosis, and infective endocarditis as the most clinically significant and potentially disabling forms of the disease. The presented material emphasizes the need for early diagnosis, comprehensive monitoring of autoimmune markers, and investigation of the long-term impact of chronic infection on health.

Keywords: Brucellosis, *Brucella*, systemic involvement, osteoarticular complications, neurobrucellosis, autoimmune markers, antinuclear antibodies.

Brucellosis is a zoonotic infectious disease caused by bacteria of the genus *Brucella*. The genus was named in honor of David Bruce, who identified *Brucella melitensis* in 1886 [1]. *Brucella* species are small, Gram-negative, non-spore-forming, non-encapsulated coccobacilli. As few as 10–100 organisms may be sufficient to cause disease in humans [2].

Twelve *Brucella* species have been identified, yet human disease is primarily caused by *B. suis*, *B. melitensis*, *B. abortus*, and *B. canis* [3]. Transmission occurs through direct contact, conjunctival exposure, ingestion via the gastrointestinal tract, inhalation, or hematogenous spread. Li N. et al. (2020) reported that laboratory-acquired infections—via aerosols or direct contact—constitute an important mode of transmission [4].

Brucellosis imposes substantial economic and public health burdens globally. Annual incidence worldwide is estimated at 5–12.5 million cases [5]. According to Głowacka P. et al. (2018), *Brucella* invades host macrophages and persists intracellularly for prolonged periods, evading immune responses and contributing to chronic infection [6].

Clinically, brucellosis manifests with nonspecific symptoms. A systematic review by Dean A. S. et al. (2012) notes common presentations such as fever, profuse sweating, fatigue, anorexia, arthralgia, skin rashes, and hepatosplenomegaly or lymphadenopathy [7]. The nonspecific clinical picture often leads to misdiagnosis and progression to chronic disease. Jin M. et al. (2023) emphasize that inadequate treatment during the acute phase may result in severe complications, disability, and even death [8].

Systemic Involvement

1. Musculoskeletal Involvement

Musculoskeletal complications represent the most frequent severe manifestations of brucellosis, with a prevalence ranging from 2–77%. Osteoarticular involvement primarily includes spondylitis, sacroiliitis, peripheral arthritis, and osteomyelitis [9].

Spondylitis: The most severe form of osteoarticular disease, commonly affecting older adults and associated with functional impairment and deformity. Reported prevalence ranges from 2% to 60% [10]. Hematogenous spread results in spondylodiscitis. Inadequate treatment can allow extension beyond vertebral structures [11].

Sacroiliitis: More common in infections caused by *B. melitensis*. Prevalence ranges from 2% to 45% and is particularly frequent in young adults (15–35 years) [8].

Peripheral Arthritis: Occurs in 14–26% of cases [12] and may manifest in all phases of disease. It affects large joints, especially the knee, hip, and ankle [13]. Hip arthritis can be more severe compared to other joints [14].

Osteomyelitis: May result in pathologic fractures or prosthetic joint involvement [15].

2. Gastrointestinal Involvement

Gastrointestinal manifestations often accompany hematologic abnormalities such as anemia or thrombocytopenia [16].

In a study of 251 patients, Pourbagher M. A. et al. (2006) reported: Splenomegaly (8.4%), Hepatomegaly (6%), Splenic abscess (1.6%), Splenic cyst (0.8%), Acute appendicitis (0.8%), Acute cholecystitis (0.4%) [17].

Brucella exploits hepatic immune tolerance mechanisms, promoting chronic infection and fibrosis [18].

It may also cause acute pancreatitis through involvement of the biliary tract or bloodstream [19].

3. Cardiovascular Involvement

Brucellosis may cause diastolic dysfunction and myocardial injury. Chronic infection contributes to endothelial dysfunction and progression of atherosclerosis [20].

Infective Endocarditis: The most severe cardiovascular complication. It predominantly affects the aortic and mitral valves [21]. Over 80% of brucellosis-related deaths are attributed to endocarditis [22]. Embolic events occur in 22–43% of cases [23].

Aortic Involvement: A life-threatening but often overlooked complication, as reported by Cascio A. et al., (2012) [24].

ECG Abnormalities: Observed in 28.7% of patients [25].

4. Hematologic Manifestations

Common in the acute phase, particularly among children. Reported frequencies: Anemia (20–53%), Leukopenia (28%), Thrombocytopenia (14%), Pancytopenia (2%) [26].

Mechanisms include disturbed iron metabolism, increased phagocytosis, myelosuppression, and autoimmune hemolysis [27].

5. Respiratory Involvement

In a study from Turkey, 92.5% of patients presented with acute infection, frequently accompanied by pneumonia [28]. Many cases are associated with consumption of unpasteurized dairy products [29].

6. Genitourinary Involvement

Reported in 2–20% of patients. The most common forms are unilateral epididymitis and orchitis [30].

In a study of 801 cases, 22 had genitourinary involvement, predominantly orchitis, epididymo-orchitis, prostatitis, and urethral stenosis [31].

Renal complications include acute interstitial nephritis/pyelonephritis, chronic renal involvement, and renal damage secondary to endocarditis [32].

7. Neurological Involvement

Neurobrucellosis occurs in 0.5–25% of patients. Mechanisms include direct invasion and immune-mediated damage [33].

Clinical forms:

- Meningitis (most common)
- Chronic peripheral neuropathy
- Diffuse CNS involvement [34].

Additional manifestations: meningoencephalitis, myelitis, radiculitis, cranial neuropathies, brain abscess [35].

SIADH (Syndrome of Inappropriate Antidiuretic Hormone Secretion) occurs in up to 21.9% of pediatric cases [36].

8. Dermatologic Manifestations

Cutaneous involvement occurs in 5–17% of cases. Lesions include:

- Disseminated papules
- Nodular eruptions (most common)
- Erythema nodosum-like lesions
- Diffuse maculopapular or purpuric rashes [37].

9. Ocular Involvement

In a study of 1551 patients, ocular involvement was found in 3.4%, and 82.7% had uveitis. Eye involvement occurs predominantly in the chronic stage and is more frequent among young women (16–35 years) [38].

10. Immune Dysregulation and Autoimmune Phenomena

Beyond direct tissue invasion and inflammation, brucellosis has been associated with immune dysregulation and the emergence of autoimmune serological markers. Elevated levels of rheumatoid factor (RF), anti-cyclic citrullinated peptide antibodies (ACPA), and, less frequently, antinuclear antibodies (ANA) have been reported in patients with brucellosis [39,40].

These findings are thought to result from polyclonal B-cell activation and nonspecific immune stimulation during chronic infectious inflammation, leading to false-positive serological results and clinical presentations that may mimic rheumatologic diseases [40,41].

In one study, ANA positivity was detected in 8% of patients, ACPA in 16.3%, and RF in 30.6%, despite the absence of clinical or diagnostic criteria for autoimmune disease [39].

This phenomenon underscores the importance of considering brucellosis in the differential diagnosis of patients presenting with musculoskeletal symptoms and positive autoimmune serology, particularly in endemic regions [39,40].

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